

GLOBAL BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT, TAXATION, AND TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION: A CATALYST FOR SMEs' RESILIENCE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examines the impact of the business environment, taxation, and technological innovation on SME resilience and economic growth in Nigeria, assessing their interactive effects within a dynamic economic context. Based on the Solow growth model with extensions to model taxation and endogenous technological change, this study employs the Generalised Linear Model (GLM) to analyse annual data for the period 1995-2023. A Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used to compute and obtain a single index for SMEs' resilience. The interactive regression specifications are used to model the interdependencies among our principal determinants or variables. The results indicate that while a stable business environment positively influences GDP growth, it does not significantly improve SME resilience due to bottlenecks in infrastructure and regulation. Taxation has combined effects where corporate income tax supports SME resilience, while VAT and aggregate tax revenue have neutral or negative effects. Technological innovation, as valuable as it is in the long term, sabotages short-run economic stability and flexibility of SMEs. Interactive analysis reveals that limitations in the business environment enhance taxation burdens, while targeted tax incentives and infrastructure investment mitigate innovation-related disruptions. The study adds to SME resilience literature by integrating business environment dynamics, the effectiveness of taxation, and technological transformation. It provides policy implications to ensure optimum SME contributions to Nigeria's economic growth.

Keywords: SME Resilience, Business Environment, Taxation, Technological Innovation, Economic Growth, Nigeria

I. INTRODUCTION

The global business environment is currently undergoing unprecedented change led by faster technological advancements, regulatory reforms, and evolving taxing regimes [1]. Nigeria, the largest African economy, is a good manifestation of this dynamic interplay. More recently, the economy has followed structural reforms focused on diversifying its revenue source away from crude oil dependence, hence, leveraging on its over 230 million people to drive economic growth [2]. The gross domestic product (GDP) of Nigeria rose from \$57.48B in 1999 to its peak at \$568.5B in 2014, declined to its lowest level of \$375.74B in 2017, before peaking to \$476.47B in 2022, which indicates growth potential and natural structural issues [3]. Within these economic activities, SMEs play a key role in Nigeria's economy, accounting for 48% of GDP, 96% of enterprises, and 84% of employment [4]. MSMEs dropped 4.5% from 41.54M (2017) to 39.65M (2020) due to the pandemic. COVID-19 hit 94.3% of businesses, with 64.5% of microenterprises making less than N50,000/month, which reflects financial vulnerability. Also, SMEs have been challenged by tax pressure, economic volatility, and global shocks, testing their resilience and innovation ([5] and [6]).

Nigerian taxation is a critical but weak source of funding, with the tax-to-GDP ratio at 7.9% in 2022, far lower than the 16.0% African average and the 15–20% developed economy standards. Corporate tax contributed 47% of the overall tax income in 2022, followed by goods and services tax (17%). Despite its 1.2 percentage point increase from 2021, Nigeria's tax collection remains structurally deficient, limiting public investment capacity [7]. The Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) has identified the factors such as multiplicity of taxes, fiscal complications, double taxation and bureaucratic inefficiencies [8]. Empirical evidence suggests that such over-the-top and complex taxation discourages business development, as SMEs are forced to spend disproportionate resources on compliance rather than innovation ([8] and [9]). Although past administration has attempted to resolve tax complications, the challenges persist, particularly in the area of placing constraints on tax jurisdictions and non-compliance [10]. In addition, financial burdens imposed by tax policies not only affect immediate operations but also have a bearing on long-term

strategic decisions, such as investment in human capital and technology, that are relevant to improving SME resilience and overall economic growth.

Technological innovations are essential in remodelling the competitive edge of Nigeria. Nigerian broadband penetration was 45.61%, mobile internet subscription was 141.67 million, and broadband subscription stood at 98.88 million. However, internet usage regularly occurs among just 29% of Nigerians. Despite these trends, poor infrastructure and high costs hinder the widespread development of broadband, leaving 27.91 million people in under-coverage areas [11]. Whereas larger firms benefit from investment in research and development (R&D) and online platforms, most SMEs are challenged by a lack of access to funds, weak technical capabilities, and infrastructural inadequacies hampering effective integration of technology into their enterprises ([12] and [13]). The intersection of an uncertain global business environment, unfavourable taxation, and asymmetric technological developments is a perplexing scenario for Nigeria's SMEs and overall economic growth [9].

Empirical studies have shown that a more effective and equitable tax regime, together with strategic investment in technological infrastructure and R&D, can significantly enhance SME resilience and long-term economic growth [14]. However, regulatory constraints, persistent infrastructural deficiencies, and often impenetrable fiscal regimes persist to suppress the potential of SMEs to contribute towards economic growth in a substantial sense ([8] and [9]). Importantly, previous research has ignored the need to individually and jointly examine how the global business environment, tax revenues, and technological innovations influence SME resilience and economic growth in Nigeria.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 1 presents the background and context, and Sections 2 and 3 cover the literature review and methodology, respectively. Section 4 presents the findings and discussion of the results, and Section 5 concludes with policy recommendations and future research directions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Theoretical Framework

The Solow growth model is a long-run economic growth model with capital accumulation, labour force increases, and technological progress as key components. This study modifies the Solow model to examine how the international business environment, taxation, and technological change influence SME resilience and economic growth. This is because SMEs are a vital component of any economy, and their resilience to shocks is influenced by government policy, access to finance, and the rate of technological advancement. The standard Solow production function is expressed as:

$$Y(t) = A(t)K(t)^\alpha L(t)^{1-\alpha} \quad (1)$$

Where $Y(t)$ is the total economic output (GDP), $A(t)$ represents total factor productivity (TFP), which captures technological progress, $K(t)$ is the capital stock, which includes physical investments by firms, including SMEs, $L(t)$ represents labour input (the workforce), and α is the capital elasticity of output, with $0 < \alpha < 1$, indicating the contribution of capital to output growth.

The model assumes decreasing returns to labour and capital, and capital accumulation is vital for SME's growth. The basic Solow model is provided by:

$$\hat{K}(t) = sY(t) - \delta K(t) \quad (2)$$

Where s is the savings rate, which determines how much income is reinvested into capital, δ is the depreciation rate, accounting for capital deterioration over time, and $\hat{K}(t)$ represents the change in capital stock over time.

Though, taxation has a major influence in deciding the extent of capital accumulated by SMEs. A large corporate tax cuts down the available retained earnings to be reinvested, slowing down the rate of capital increase. Adding taxation (τ) to the above equation, it becomes:

$$\hat{K}(t) = s(1 - \tau)Y(t) - \delta K(t) \quad (3)$$

Where τ is the rate of tax on SME profits. Tax burden (τ) rise lowers savings, discourages investment and limit SME's growth. Conversely, lowered taxes or tax concessions might boost business growth and resistance. An efficient

international business environment with favourable tax policies, capital availability, and investor-friendly legislation can facilitate the buildup of capital, ensuring SMEs grow and support the economy [15].

In the original Solow model, technological change $A(t)$ is taken to be an exogenous variable. Modern variants of the model, however, incorporate endogenous technological change, recognising that technological innovation, research and development (R&D) expenditure, and digitalisation enhance growth. With endogenous technological innovation added, we modify the TFP equation as:

$$\hat{A}(t) = \lambda A(t) + \theta I(t)^\gamma \quad (4)$$

Where λ represents autonomous technological progress, $I(t)$ denote investment in innovation, technology, and R&D, θ measures the efficiency of technology adoption, and γ is the elasticity of innovation investment, with $\gamma > 0$ indicating increasing returns to technology adoption [16].

Steady-state economic growth relies on technological and capital growth. The long-run rate of growth in which there is taxation and technological progress is represented as:

$$g_Y = g_A + \alpha g_K \quad (5)$$

Where g_Y is the long-run economic growth rate, g_A is the growth rate of technological innovation, g_K is the growth rate of capital accumulation. Equation (5) indicates that the long-term economic growth relies on increasing g_A through R&D, technological innovation, credits, tax and business environment to enhance g_K .

B. Methodology

1. Data and Scope

This study utilises annual data on the global business environment, tax, and innovation to examine their impacts on SME resilience and economic growth in Nigeria between 1995 and 2023. The dataset captures key macroeconomic and policy-relevant indicators that are relevant to the Nigerian business environment. SME resilience and economic growth are the dependent variables of this study. While economic development is quantitatively measured using GDP growth, SME resilience will be quantitatively measured in Section 3.3 via a factor PCA to construct an SME resilience index based on multiple indicators. Business environment index, tax revenue, and technological innovation are the independent variables of primary importance to understand SME performance and economic development. Data for the variables have been obtained from reputable international and local data sources, such as World Bank Development Indicator (WDI), Economic Freedom House (EFH), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), US Federal Reserve (FRED), and the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS).

2. Model Specification and Methodology

Expanding upon the research of [17], which examined the interplay between human capital, technology, and economic growth in Nigeria, this study investigates the key drivers of the business environment, taxation, and technological innovation and their impact on SMEs' resilience and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. Consequently, the core equations for the model specification are developed as follows:

$$SME_t|GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BUS_t + \beta_2 TECH_t + \beta_3 TAX_t + \beta_4 CIT_t + \beta_5 VAT_t + \beta_6 FDI_t + \beta_7 INFRA_t + \beta_8 CAP_t + \beta_9 LAB_t + \beta_{10} INTR_t + \beta_{11} INF_t + \beta_{12} EXHR_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (6)$$

Specifically, the interactive roles among business environment, taxation, and technological innovation in influencing SME resilience and economic growth is given as:

$$SME_t|GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 (BUS_t * TECH_t) + \alpha_2 (BUS_t * TAX_t) + \alpha_3 (TAX_t * TECH_t) + \alpha_4 (BUS_t * TECH_t * TAX_t) + \alpha_5 (BUS_t * CIT_t) + \alpha_6 (BUS_t * VAT_t) + \alpha_7 (TECH_t * CIT_t) + \alpha_8 (TECH_t * VAT_t) + \mu_{it} \quad (7)$$

The coefficients of the variables in each model are represented by $\beta_1 - \beta_{12}$ and $\alpha_1 - \alpha_8$, respectively. Furthermore, ε and μ denote the stochastic error terms, and t represents the time effect. SME Resilience Index (SMERI) is computed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on three key dimensions: Commercial banks' loans to SMEs as a percentage of total credit, natural logarithm of share of SMEs contribution to GDP, and domestic credit to private sector as a percentage of GDP [18].

This study utilises the Generalised Linear Model (GLM) as its method of estimation. The GLM extends the usual linear regression model to permit the dependent variable to be a member of any of the exponential family of distributions, hence suitable for handling non-Gaussian data, heteroskedasticity, and nonlinear link functions [19]. The adaptability of the GLM model allows it to incorporate a variety of models like Gaussian, Binomial, Poisson, Gamma, and Inverse Gaussian, and thus it is a robust approach to data analysis structures most commonly found in economics, business, and finance research. The GLM model equation is as follows:

$$Y_i \sim EF(\theta_i, \phi) \quad (8)$$

Y_i = exponential family distribution, θ_i = canonical parameter, and ϕ = dispersion parameter. The expected value of Y_i is linked to the linear predictor. GLM accounts for distributional irregularities, heteroskedasticity, and nonlinear association to verify the reliability of the estimates under statistical considerations.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1 PCA Analysis

PCA in Table 1 indicates that the first principal component (Comp1) explains 90.4% of the variance in the SME Resilience Index, reinforcing its dominance in explaining resilience dynamics. The eigenvalue of 2.712 for Comp1 is much larger than the remaining components, confirming its explanatory role in measuring SME resilience from 1995 to 2023.

Table 1: PCA Computation for SME Resilience Index

Component	Eigenvalue	Difference	Proportion	Cumulative
Comp1	2.712	2.473	0.904	0.904
Comp2	0.239	0.190	0.080	0.984
Comp3	0.049		0.016	1.000

Source: Author's Computation

2 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of Table 2 are crucial to the examination of the distribution and variation of study variables during the 29 years. GDP growth is 1.852 with an extreme standard deviation that accounts for the variability of economic performance between -4.162 and 12.276. SME resilience has a mean of 0.000 with a standard deviation of 1.647, capturing moderate variability and positive and negative changes in resilience. The business environment average is at 5.581, which describes relatively stable conditions, while high dispersion, with a mean of 13.178 in technological innovation, emphasises uneven technological progress. Tax revenue, VAT, and company income tax, with moderate volatility. FDI has a mean of 3.201 but with high volatility, which emphasises investment instability.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Label	Variable Description	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GDP_t	Gross domestic product	29	1.852	3.378	-4.162	12.276
SME_t	SMEs resilience	29	0.000	1.647	-3.514	1.651
BUS_t	Business environment	29	5.581	1.193	3.280	6.760
$TECH_t$	Technological innovation	29	13.178	12.790	0.000	35.500
TAX_t	Tax revenue	29	8.359	1.098	6.131	9.865
VAT_t	Value added tax	29	5.762	1.440	3.035	7.981
CIT_t	Company income tax	29	5.763	1.571	3.084	8.116
FDI_t	Foreign direct investment	29	3.201	2.743	-0.200	8.840
$INFRA_t$	Infrastructural development	29	50.355	6.539	38.687	60.500
CAP_t	Capital stock	29	6.403	0.040	6.337	6.462
LAB_t	Labour stock	29	7.871	0.096	7.712	8.042
$INTR_t$	Lending interest rate	29	17.597	2.958	11.483	24.771
$INFL_t$	Inflation rate	29	15.252	12.285	5.388	72.836
$EXHR_t$	Exchange rate	29	116.798	47.874	69.198	273.013

Source: Author's Computation

3 Stability of the Time Series Data

The DF-GLS stationarity test in Table 3 confirms the order of integration of the study variables. GDP, labour stock, inflation, and exchange rate are level-stationary, I (0). Conversely, SME resilience, business environment, technological innovation, tax revenue, VAT, company income tax, foreign direct investment, infrastructural development, capital stock, and lending interest rate are non-stationary at the level but stationary after first differencing, confirming their integration at I (1). The results show that most macroeconomic and financial variables are unit-root, which reflects the presence of long-run trends requiring differencing to make econometric modelling accurate. The presence of I (0) and I (1) variables warrants the use of generalized linear model that can handle such characteristics and deliver robust inference.

Table 3: Dickey-Fuller Generalised Least Squares Stationarity Test

Variable	Test Statistic		Critical Value (CV)			Order of Integration
	Level	1 st Diff.	1% CV	5% CV	10% CV	
GDP_t	1.731	-3.122	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (0)
SME_t	-0.790	-3.485	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
BUS_t	-0.904	-3.270	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
$TECH_t$	-0.418	-1.201	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
TAX_t	-0.459	-4.494	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
VAT_t	0.659	-2.058	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
CIT_t	0.122	-3.188	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
FDI_t	-1.051	-3.279	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
$INFRA_t$	-0.098	-6.139	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
CAP_t	-0.327	-2.790	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
LAB_t	1.885	-0.719	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (0)
$INTR_t$	-1.538	-3.722	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (1)
$INFL_t$	-1.178	-1.140	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (0)
$EXHR_t$	-2.580	-3.620	-2.654	-1.950	-1.602	I (0)

Source: Author's Computation

4 Main Results

The estimation in Table 4 shows the impact of business environment, taxation, and technological innovation on SME resilience and economic growth in Nigeria. A good business environment strongly and positively impacts GDP growth, but does not significantly impact SME resilience, which shows macroeconomic benefits without the direct SME-level improvement. Technological innovation is detrimental to both GDP and SME resilience, indicating that while innovation is a core element of long-term productivity, its short-run disruptive effects may limit economic growth and SME resilience. Taxation variables (company income tax, VAT, and tax revenue) have mixed effects, with a positive effect on SME resilience being exerted by company income tax, yet both VAT and tax revenue are statistically insignificant.

Table 4: Effect of Business Environment, Taxation, and Technological Innovation on SME Resilience and Economic Growth

VARIABLE	GDP _t	SME _t
BUS _t	0.798** (0.038)	-0.018 (0.926)
TECH _t	-0.275** (0.007)	-0.110*** (0.000)
TAX _t	-0.216 (0.774)	-0.457 (0.126)
VAT _t	1.736 (0.151)	-0.286 (0.357)
CIT _t	0.783 (0.131)	1.311*** (0.000)
FDI _t	-0.168*** (0.000)	0.098*** (0.000)
INFRA _t	-0.029** (0.054)	-0.027** (0.002)
CAP _t	-196.104*** (0.000)	6.200 (0.606)
LAB _t	71.668*** (0.000)	16.007** (0.001)
INTR _t	0.173* (0.081)	-0.015 (0.139)
INFL _t	-0.057** (0.005)	-0.004* (0.096)
EXHR _t	0.005 (0.349)	-0.001 (0.324)
C _t	676.774** (0.009)	-164.707** (0.034)
N	29	29

Source: Author's Computation.

Notably, p-values are in parentheses. *** denotes a 1% significant level, ** implies a 5% significant level, and * is the 10% significant level.

Table 5 estimate provides additional evidence on the combined effect of the business environment, taxation, and technological innovation on SME resilience and economic growth in Nigeria. There is an interaction between the business environment and technological innovation to impact GDP negatively but SME resilience positively, implying that while technological change can be a disruptor of general economic stability, it enhances SME adaptability. The combined effect of business environment and taxation has a significant negative effect on GDP and SME resilience, which means that tax burden in the face of an unstable business environment chokes economic growth and SME resilience. Nevertheless, the combined effect of technological innovation and taxation has a positive effect on GDP and SME resilience, which suggests that good tax policies can propel technology-led growth. Triple interaction between business environment, taxation, and technological innovation is significantly positive for GDP but significantly negative for SME resilience, suggesting the difficulty of policy trade-offs. Business environment interactions with company income tax lower GDP but heighten SME resilience, suggesting that company income tax enables SME stability in the face of general economic constraints. Value-added tax interaction with the business environment provides mixed evidence, positively affecting GDP but not significantly affecting SME resilience. The interaction of technological innovation and company income tax has a significant positive impact on GDP, suggesting that corporate taxation, when coupled with technological innovation, supports economic growth. However, its influence on SME resilience is statistically insignificant. In contrast, the interaction between technological innovation and value-added tax, albeit not influential on SME resilience, negatively impacts GDP significantly, implying that

VAT can constrain the economic benefits of technological innovation, perhaps by contributing to the cost burden of technology-based companies.

Table 5: Interactive Roles of Business Environment, Taxation, and Technological Innovation on SME Resilience and Economic Growth

VARIABLE	GDP_t	SME_t
$BUS_t * TECH_t$	-0.288*** (0.000)	0.018** (0.005)
$BUS_t * TAX_t$	-1.044** (0.013)	-0.087*** (0.000)
$TECH_t * TAX_t$	0.357* (0.063)	0.032*** (0.000)
$BUS_t * TECH_t * TAX_t$	0.038*** (0.000)	-0.010*** (0.000)
$BUS_t * CIT_t$	-1.497** (0.028)	0.174** (0.019)
$BUS_t * VAT_t$	3.149** (0.015)	0.093 (0.296)
$TECH_t * CIT_t$	0.994** (0.013)	-0.001 (0.943)
$TECH_t * VAT_t$	-1.638** (0.021)	0.014 (0.531)
C_t	1.215 (0.174)	-3.943*** (0.000)
N	29	29

Source: Author's Computation.

Notably, p-values are in parentheses. *** denotes a 1% significant level, ** implies a 5% significant level, and * is the 10% significant level.

5. Discussion

The findings confirm the weakness of the business environment, taxation, and technological innovation in facilitating SME resilience and economic growth. While a good business environment drives GDP growth, its lack of impact on SMEs reflects systemic barriers such as infrastructure inefficiencies, unpredictable regulatory regimes, and bureaucratic bottlenecks [15]. The adverse effect of technological innovation on GDP and SME resilience, as well as the underdevelopment of Nigeria's industrial and digital economies remain major setback in support of [20]. In terms of tax, company income tax increases SME resilience but stifles GDP, illustrating a corporate tax regime that provides revenue stability for small enterprises but limits overall capital accumulation [18]. Meanwhile, VAT's slight impact on SME resilience but negative impact on GDP suggests that indirect taxation contributes to the financial burden on businesses and consumers, suppressing economic momentum [10]. The overall impact of taxation and technological innovation has a positive impact on GDP and SME resilience, demonstrating that tax incentives framed in the appropriate manner can spur technology-led growth. However, the interaction of business environment, taxation, and technological innovation negatively affects SME resilience, reflecting policy trade-offs where aggressive fiscal measures and regulatory inconsistency undermine SME adjustment [21]. These disclosures underscore the need for proportionate tax reforms, effective infrastructure and innovation-oriented policies to foster an SME-friendly business climate and sustain economic development [22].

IV. CONCLUSION

The findings of this paper underscore the complex dynamics between the business environment, taxation, and technological innovation in shaping SME resilience and Nigerian economic growth. While a good business environment triggers GDP growth, its benefits do not pass through completely to SME resilience. Taxation has diverse effects—corporate tax appears to foster SME resilience, while VAT and tax revenue have negative impacts on SME resilience and growth. Though technological innovation is a critical long-term growth driver, it has short-term negative effects on GDP and SME resilience. This implies weak absorptive capacity and structural vulnerabilities of the digital economy. To develop SME resilience and foster economic growth, policymakers should give high priority to tax reforms that reduce compliance costs and revenue leakage and ensure a well-balanced tax system that encourages business growth and innovation. In addition, investment in technology infrastructure, digital literacy, and special SME financing must be enhanced to close the gap in innovation. The government should also enhance the business climate through effective regulatory mechanisms, easier access to credit, and effective infrastructure to reduce the cost of doing business for SMEs. Further, an overall policy framework with a mix of tax incentives, technology-driven business solutions, and institutional support interventions is required to provide a more robust and competitive SME sector in Nigeria. Future research should aim to investigate the sectoral impacts of taxation policy and innovation adoption, as well as the moderating influence of financial inclusion between the volatility of the business environment and firm performance.

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